

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

Target specificity of *Drosophila* PAX6 transcription factor homologs

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

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Based on

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I. Data areas and data types

The project will create non-human (*Drosophila melanogaster*) data exclusively. The data consists of: high-throughput (HT) sequencing data for measuring transcript expression levels (bulk RNA-seq): 20 samples (4 wild-type, 4 ey overexpression, 4 ey knockdown, 4 toy overexpression, 4 toy knockdown) will be sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq X Plus Series sequencer, 150bp paired-end reads to a depth of 20M reads.

Results will be stored in compressed FASTQ format with a size of approximately 6GB per sample. TOTAL file size: approximately 120GB. HT sequencing data of transcription factor binding profiles (CUT&RUN): 8 samples (4 ey, 4 toy) will be sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq X Plus Series sequencer, 150bp paired-end reads to a depth of 8M reads. Results will be stored in compressed FASTQ format with a size of approximately 2.4GB per sample. TOTAL file size: approximately 19.2GB. Associated metadata: sample data such as transcription factor analysed, tissue, developmental stage and technical metadata such as sequence library metrics, sequencer, etc. Data analysis: absolute and relative expression levels relative to wild-type stored as tab-separated text files for RNAseq and BigBED files with peak calling for CUT&RUN experiments. TOTAL file size: less than 1GB

II. Standards and metadata

HT sequencing data: Metadata for each experiment will be stored in MAGE-TAB format (doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-7-489) to MINSEQE standards (zenodo.org/record/5706412) as required by the public repository, ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress). Biological metadata will be further refined (organism, strain, developmental stage, sex, tissue and genotype) and stored in Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO) format.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

New primary data will be generated for both RNA-seq and CUT&RUN experiments.

IV. Secondary use

Researchers studying transcription factor specificity, especially of PAX6 transcription factors in other model organisms or in humans, will benefit from this dataset.

V. Methods for data sharing

All data will be available through a web interface to the dedicated server. In addition, data will be available through the public repository ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress).

VI. Proprietary data

We anticipate no restrictions or delays to data sharing.

VII. Timeframes

All data will be made available upon publication, or within three years of generation of the dataset, whichever comes first. No further restrictions or delays are anticipated.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

Raw HT sequencing data format will be compressed FASTQ. Analysed data for RNA-seq experiments will consist of absolute (read counts) and relative (\log_2 fold change) expression levels relative to wild-type stored as tab-separated text files. For CUT&RUN experiments, the analysed data will consist of BigBED files with peak calling.